

Rapid Thin Layer Chromatographic Separation of some Aromatic Amines using Surfactants

RAJEEV JAIN* and SEEMA GUPTA

School of Studies in Chemistry, Jiwaji University, Gwalior-474 011

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Due to industrial, toxicological and pharmaceutical applications¹ of aromatic amines, thin layer chromatographic separation and detection of various aromatic amines have been carried out by several workers².

The present paper describes the resolution of thirteen aromatic amines using various surfactants as mobile phase or stationary phase. Efforts were also made to separate amines by making use of various solvents.

Results and Discussion

When aromatic amines were spotted and irrigated on chromatographic plates they resolved distinctly. When silica gel-G impregnated with 1% cetyltrimethylammonium bromide was developed with benzene + chloroform (40 : 60) solvent system proper separation could not be achieved. First attempts were made to separate aromatic amines using various polar and non-polar solvents as mobile phase. However, out of many combinations tried, benzene + chloroform (40 : 60) was proved reasonably satisfactory and only six out of thirteen amine could be separated. The efforts were made to separate these aromatic amines using various solvents in sequence. While using chloroform-acetone-carbon tetrachloride, eleven out of thirteen amines could be separated. The sequential use of solvents as an alternative to these solvents mixture in chromatography is an unexplored field.

To achieve better separations these amines were also separated using cationic, anionic and

non-ionic surfactants as mobile phase. Best separation was achieved when 2% sodium dodecyl sulphate was used as solvent. But when 1% Tween-20 was used as solvent, most of the amines did not moved. With solvent systems 2% cetyl pyridinium chloride, 2% Tween-20, 3% Tween-20 and 2% cetyltrimethylammonium bromide, good separations could not be achieved.

With most of the solvents systems, 4-hexylaniline and 4-heptylaniline could be separated properly. Thin coatings of the adsorbents produced good resolutions. As expected there existed an interesting relationship between R_f and the size of alkyl group.

Experimental

An ascending irrigation technique was employed using glass plates (20 cm × 20 cm). The aromatic amines were carefully recrystallised before spotting. The following adsorbents were employed : (A) silica gel-G (E. Merck, throughout) and (B) silica gel-G with cetyltrimethylammonium bromide.

The thin layer chromatographic plates (thickness 0.5 mm) were prepared using a slurry of the above adsorbents in distilled water. Solutions of aromatic amines in methanol were spotted on the plates. The plates were dried at room temperature and then irrigated with different solvent systems. The spots were observed by placing the plates in NO_2 gas chamber. R_f values of the various aromatic amines are listed in Table I.

TABLE 1— R_f ($\times 100$) VALUES OF AROMATIC AMINES

Sl. no.	Amine	Silica gel-G*					Silica gel-G + 1% cetyl-trimethylammonium bromide
		(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	
1.	<i>o</i> -Toluidine	42	52	29	37	79	59
2.	<i>m</i> -Toluidine	41	68	32	33	76	54
3.	<i>p</i> -Toluidine	31	72	26	47	62	40
4.	2,5-Dimethylaniline	41	38	33	35	73	61
5.	2,3-Dimethylaniline	35	18	31	28	71	34
6.	4-Ethylaniline	56	34	21	26	68	40
7.	4-Butylaniline	58	0	0	14	75	46
8.	1,2-Phenyldiamine	28	83	59	62	73	0
9.	<i>N,N</i> -Dimethylbenzylamine	50	35	29	27	84	22
10.	Aniline	40	67	40	49	90	26
11.	4-Pentylaniline	33	12	0	22	56	33
12.	4-Hexylaniline	46	9	17	18	92	41
13.	4-Heptylaniline	31	36	0	22	81	28

*Solvent systems : (1) 40 ml benzene + 60 ml chloroform; (2) 2% sodium dodecyl sulphate; (3) 3% Tween-20; (4) 2% cetyltrimethylammonium bromide; (5) chloroform-acetone-carbon tetrachloride in sequence.

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